

Generative Language Models in Education: Foreign Language Learning and the Teacher as Prompt Engineer

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Abstract: *Generative language models are powerful tools trained on a large digital corpus, and their capability to generate novel text to specification has received significant press for possible interference in education as teachers face submissions which are potentially machine-generated. These problems are acknowledged and elaborated here, but focus is then shifted to how these systems might more productively be inserted into the educational process in the future. The instructional potential of such systems for aspects of foreign language education are explored in an excursive manner, and in the context of arguing that teachers, far from being displaced, will take on a supplementary role as expert user in extracting from these systems precisely what is required for student learning to occur. Such a role is notionally similar to that of “prompt engineer” and identifies an additional and reconfigured space for the teacher as an “educational prompt engineer” of sorts.*

Keywords: generative language models, GLM, GLMs, foreign language education, teaching practice, prompt engineer, educational prompt engineer, pedagogical prompt engineer, prompt engineering for education

Generative language models (GLMs) and their deployment in the public domain through chatbots such as ChatGPT (which uses the Generative Pre-trained Transformer architecture and became publicly accessible on November 30, 2022) have generated considerable discussion as the implications of the technology are digested and absorbed. The level of public interest reflects an awareness that the technology presents paradigm-shifting capabilities for interacting with the corpus of information accumulated in digital space; a corpus now so large that abundance has superseded dearth as the primary problem for location and access. Just as the Graphical User Interface (GUI) revolutionized our interaction with the computer (moving us from the tedious task of text-based commands to an interface more simulative of our interaction with the push-button, tactile world), so too, GLMs revolutionize our interaction with accumulated information in public space by replacing the skill-based process of honed searches of stored sources (basically retrieval actions only)

with something more closely resembling the way we act as informational agents in human-to-human interaction. As with all emerging technologies, conversation quickly turns from the immediate and intended solutions which a new technology provides (which are often viewed as liberating) to a broader examination of the full range of consequences it might have (which are often viewed more equivocally). Much of the latter form of conversation will, of course, revolve around potential disruption. In this regard, GLMs have, for example, received significant attention for, among others, their potential displacement of various forms of white-collar work, their production of bias (even propaganda under the wrong hands), the inability of humans to distinguish output as being artificially produced, and the prospect of a digital corpus which increasingly moves toward being machine-based (as machine output starts being uploaded to it) and therefore belying the human corpus upon which the technology was initially birthed.

GLMs and Disruption in Education

One very visible domain with respect to the issue of disruption is education. The technology is obviously a challenge to teachers who need to evaluate authentic written production submitted by students and who know that, outside of direct observation during such production, it is always possible that they are evaluating machine capabilities rather than student capabilities. There is a limited constraint on this at the moment, in the case of ChatGPT for example, given age restrictions on signing up for services (OpenAI, 2023), but this is only a temporary contingency in what is clearly an overall and gathering concern. The challenge of distinguishing authentic student output from machine output is an amplification of the more familiar problem of identifying student plagiarism. It is actually much easier for the student to request machine-generated output (with a high degree of specification) than it is to plagiarize, and also exponentially more difficult for the teacher to notice this and more especially prove it. GLMs are, as the name implies, generating novel text on the basis of a very large training corpus, and not merely duplicating chunks of that corpus. Traditional plagiarism involves duplication of chunks of text from stored sources, and because duplication is involved these duplications can potentially be correlated by the teacher. When a student uses a GLM like ChatGPT to substitute for their own authentic production, they are really engaged in a form of distributed plagiarism because the output of the GLM does ultimately have a source (the corpus on which it is trained), but this corpus is not being replicated in the generated output, or at least not in any simplistic sense. As such, the teacher cannot locate a stored source for the students' GLM-produced output. We can envisage services from GLM providers or others to fulfill this need to identify machine output in the future, but for now the problem exists, and the most recent attempts at solutions have failed to distinguish AI-generated content from human-generated content (OpenAI, 2023). These kinds of problems for education have already received significant press, and public awareness of them has now moved beyond the profession to the person on the street. The problem is easier to manage in the classroom where the teacher has eyes, but for work conducted beyond the classroom the problem is quite significant.

The Teacher and GLMs in Education

While these are important problems which should be acknowledged and which have already captured much of the attention around GLMs and education thus far, they should not overwhelm

efforts to look down range at how these technologies might impact education in ways which are positive, or at least less-obviously negative. Central to this will be understanding how GLMs can be situated within the educational process appropriately, and understanding how this might also reconfigure the relationship between teacher and student and, therefore, the role of the teacher. Speculating about a changing role for the teacher on account of GLMs will inevitably provoke some reflexive and even emotional responses, but such change should not by itself be disconcerting as the role of the teacher has always been contested and subject to reconfiguration; witness, for example, the recent move away from the teacher-centered classroom (Keiler, 2018). Change which is improperly understood, and therefore improperly managed, is usually not beneficial, and the converse is also true. In the case of GLMs like ChatGPT, it is arguable that the potential for disruption in education is also the potential for progress if the place of the technology in the learning process is properly configured and managed, and that this will also require at least partial reconfiguration of everything else, including the teacher/student relationship and the role of teacher.

Perhaps the most problematic issue with the student submitting GLM-produced work (distributed plagiarism), is that it undermines the teacher's desire to assess the student accurately and calibrate further instruction; that is, it gets between the student and the teacher in a manner subversive to the proper agency of the teacher (and this is, of course, completely aside from the ethical issue of it being a violation of the honor code). From a pedagogical point of view, the value of the teacher is not so much in disseminating knowledge (though this is part of the role), as it is in comprehending the state of progress of the student's developing mind and calibrating teaching (the action of one mind upon another) to this. To comprehend this state of progress, the teacher needs to make observations which most typically involve interaction with the student and receiving samples of student output such as essays and responses to test questions and so on. This is essentially an issue of knowledge of other minds, and of the teacher being an expert and evidence-based knower of other minds in a specific field of competence (Isemonger, 2020).

From a theoretical and pedagogical point of view, such notions of the real value of the teacher as expert knower of other minds are probably best expressed within sociocultural theory and the work of important theorists such as Vygotsky (1978, 1986). The perspective offered in sociocultural theory is underpinned by a primary theoretical assumption (inherited from Marxist epistemology) that society precedes mind and not the other way around. In other words, society is not so much the aggregation of individual minds which have developed in individual engagement with the objective world – a sort of epiphenomenon of the collectivization of individual minds – as it is the very constructor of mind itself. Vygotsky's contribution was in providing psychological explanation of how this social construction of mind in the process of child development occurs, and his principle insights revolve around the agency of the social other in regulating the developing mind in advance of maturity (with maturity being defined as the point where regulation by the other is replaced by self-regulation). Theoretical constructs such as the zone of proximal development (or ZPD) were offered as a model to conceptualize the appropriate space in which the external agent (parent, teacher, or more experienced social other) must operate to leverage the child through learning what he or she is ready to learn. This cognitive space (the ZPD) is defined by the tasks (cognitive or otherwise) which the child is able to execute under guidance but not alone. If you teach in a space before the ZPD, you are teaching what the child already knows. If you teach in a space after it, you are teaching what the child is not ready to learn. While initially advanced as a theoretical account of child development, Vygotsky's work has been extended to classroom pedagogy more

generally, whether this be with respect to children or adults. This conceptualization of the agency of the other in regulating the individual's learning is institutionally formalized in education by the role of the teacher, and regulation in the appropriate learning space (the ZPD) should be considered the primary expertise of the teacher and not the simple transfer of information. As stated above, most of the attention with respect to GLMs like ChatGPT and education have focused on the subversion of this critical role which the teacher plays. The positive prospects for GLMs, however, would seem to exist in consideration of their capacity to substitute for, rather than obstruct, the teacher and to do so in ways which are purposeful and empowering to both teacher and student.

Limitations of GLMs in Substituting for the Teacher

Any critical examination of the prospects for teacher substitution by the GLM and for GLM/student interactions becoming another site for learning should be assisted by the same theoretical understandings (sociocultural) as have been outlined immediately above with respect to the traditional teacher/student dyad, and specifically understandings which do not configure the teacher as mere agent for the transfer of information. The system too (in this case the GLM-based system), if it is to be educationally useful, needs to be more than a transferrer of information. Any long-term role for GLMs beyond simply answering questions and generating text to specification will hinge on the ability to assess and model the state of progress of the learner in calibrating interaction (instruction and feedback) to an appropriate level. So, there are two core issues here: 1) the information about the user available to the GLM in the field of competence for which he or she is purposefully interacting for learning purposes, and 2) the capacity to regulate output sent to the user to this competence level. Now of course, and with respect to GLMs like ChatGPT, we are not there yet, and furthermore modeling the mind of the user is outside of the scope of what current GLMs like ChatGPT do and, in fact, actually are. Their modeling is focused on the corpus upon which they are trained and on how they are to respond to explicit requests or prompts from the user. Also, and interestingly, capacities for the assessment of the competence of a learner and delivery of content based on this assessment precede GLMs and are not new in computer-assisted instruction and associated areas such as instructional design. Indeed, the process of testing students and presenting appropriate-level instruction (often in an iterative way) is quite well established (for reviews of related systems and research see Chen, Zou, Xie, & Cheng, 2021; Weng & Chiu, 2023). However, current systems which do this are generally not generative systems but rather are pre-designed, structured to a particular competence or curriculum, and therefore subject to greater strictures. With respect to GLMs, however, it may be that while 1) is currently not possible, this does not necessarily imply that 2) is impossible, provided that we precisely and explicitly tell the GLM what is required in order to regulate output to desired competence levels and requirements.

Given the very recent emergence of GLMs, it is to be expected that public research on their capabilities to fulfil some of these capacities which human teachers have (or should have) is limited. In this context and at this very early stage, it is worth exploring even in an excursive way what the prospects might be for these systems, while acknowledging that in their current state they are not capable of, nor purposed for, modeling the mind of the user. A GLM like ChatGPT might be trained on a very large corpus of digital information, but its knowledge of the specific user it is dealing with is restricted to the chat sequence in which it responds, and inquiry to ChatGPT itself (at the time of writing this paper) will confirm this. The capacity of the system to model its

responses is therefore directly governed by the specificity with which it is prompted (so it performs under explicit direction) and within a chat thread, though of course, a feature of the technology is obviously to “remember” preexisting interactional turns in formulating subsequent turns, and it is this which provides a user/system experience which is interactional or conversational. This also means that the specificity of stipulating to the system what is required can accrue within the chat sequence, and does not have to be perfect in the opening prompt. It is, however, not difficult to imagine that increasing interest in the prospects of these systems for tutoring might lead to changes in the future where more information about the learner is accumulated by the system across chat sequences. This will inevitably be attended by research into how well such a system can “know” the mind, so to speak, of the individual being tutored, and how well this “knowledge” can be used to calibrate interaction. This of course would involve a surrender of information to the system with all the concerns around privacy and the permanent storage of such information being present. Students in human-to-human interaction are surrendering information about their competence to the teacher all the time (after all teaching would not be able to occur without this), but this is to one person and as the years proceed and the teacher refocuses on new cohorts of students, the student benefits from the right to be forgotten for all intents and purposes.

The Teacher as Educational “Prompt Engineer”

Given that, for human-to-human teaching or tutoring, calibration of output by the teacher to the learner’s level of competence in a targeted area depends on knowledge of that competence, and given the aforementioned limitations we currently have with respect to these systems’ knowledge of the user, one approach, at least, is to cover for this by instructing the system on the level and format for delivery of instruction or feedback, and then to examine this from a critical perspective for instructional potential. What is pertinent about this is that instructing the system in this way is not straightforward and is actually a skill in its own right. A particular facility for such, with respect to educational use, would be notionally related to the role associated with what has popularly come to be known as a “prompt engineer” (Mihail, 2022). This is a relatively recent term associated with the emergence of GLMs, and references some form of trained capacity to get out of the GLM precisely what is required. In terms of the legacy search-engine manner of interacting with knowledge from the digital corpus (again, location and extraction only), which GLMs like ChatGPT now potentially replace and supersede, certain skills have been required which include things like distinguishing keywords which pull up the information required, enumerating more of these keywords to increase precision, excluding certain words to be even more precise, and so on. These kinds of search operations and ways of thinking are fundamentally underpinned by the logic of set theory and associated area of Boolean propositional logic (AND/OR/NOT etc.), and even if this is not explicitly recognized by the user or dealt with very consciously, it does nonetheless inevitably involve a skill to at least think in a way which is informally consistent with such theory. Similarly, while interaction with GLMs may have a more natural conversational feel, this does not mean that getting what you want is necessarily easy, and some will be better at it than others, and of course, like search, one can become better at it too. It is a skill therefore, and the nominalization of these skills as a specific expertise under the label “prompt engineer” flags the continuing role of humans (and therefore potentially teachers) in using these systems. This should not be viewed as a limitation of the current state of GLMs either, as skill in interacting with GLMs will probably be a

persistent issue if natural human interaction is anything to go on. After all, we function as skilled informational agents in authentic human-to-human interactional space, and some are better at doing this than others, and some are even specialized in it. Lawyers, police investigators, investigative reporters, counsellors, talk-show hosts and any number of other roles are all associated with specialized skills in getting particular kinds of information in a desired manner. Why would it be any other way when interacting with these artificial systems? They will never be able to read our minds (we hope), and we will need to interact with them, and doing so will be a skill, sometimes in the mundane sense and at other times in a specialized sense.

From the perspective of education, being a “prompt engineer” of sorts, but with a domain specialization in education, is at least one way in which we can reimagine a supplementary and reconfigured space for the teacher. This may involve, at first, being the specialized educational prompt engineer in supervised use of a GLM for learning purposes, but later, the stewardship of such prompt engineering skills in the student in order to further empower him or her to work more autonomously and productively with the system to his or her own learning ends. Domain specialization for the educational prompt engineer might become even more narrow and be restricted to a particular subject area of education such as mathematics, science, foreign language learning and so on. If we take the latter, foreign language learning, there is a lot which can be said about the potential for these generative systems and how teachers may become involved in helping students to exploit them (and a brief excursion into this is covered below). GLMs offer enormous prospects for overcoming some of the most intractable problems of foreign language learning, foremost of which would be providing the conversational practice which is part of the inevitable but essential grind of becoming proficient in a language.

A Place for GLMs in Foreign Language Education

GLM systems, at the most routine level, would naturally be useful for explicit knowledge inquiries by the student; that is, questions about grammar rules, word derivations and use. It is here that the interaction would take the form of direct questions and correspond fairly clearly with how these systems may typically be used by the average user in day-to-day engagement with the system; essentially a more familiar way to extract information from the digital corpus. Here the system is functioning as transferrer of information basically. The ability of the student to actually get appropriate information out of the system hinges also on what the student already knows, and sometimes this condition may not be met and here the teacher assists in a reconfigured role. However, and when it comes to foreign language learning, GLM systems could also be useful simply for the interaction itself; that is, for providing the conversational practice which is the tedium of becoming proficient in a foreign language. It is well known that the process of proceduralizing explicit knowledge about the target language (knowledge learned consciously about grammar and vocabulary and so on), so that the student can speak with the accuracy and natural automaticity characterizing native-speaker speech, is hard won and gathered through extensive practice (interaction) and importantly assisted by ongoing corrective feedback (Ellis, 2005). The importance of this interactional learning (Gass, 1997) is so much so that a formal hypothesis, namely, the interaction hypothesis (Long, 1981), as well as extensive and associated trajectories of research, most especially corrective feedback research (Li, 2010), have emerged to better understand how interaction works as the vehicle for language acquisition. Providing opportunities for this kind

of interactional learning (conversation basically, but with corrective feedback built in) is a central concern for foreign language teachers and students. It even informs contemporary teaching approaches such as communicative language teaching (CLT; Canale & Swain, 1980; Lightbown & Spada, 1990) and the associated and adjacent approach of task-based language teaching (TBLT; Nunan, 1989; Plonsky & Kim, 2016), where the entire method is geared towards providing opportunities for such authentic conversational interaction.

It is, however, not that easy to furnish opportunities for extensive conversational interaction in the classroom, and doing so is attended by a number of problems. For example, in a large class, the teacher has few opportunities to interact with each student, and while this can be partially overcome by getting students to interact with each other, there are problems here too, such as foreign language students not having confidence in the corrective feedback of other foreign language students (who are after all students as well). Overall contact times for the class may be limited as well. Students often seek solutions for the deficit by, among other things, attending private conversational schools (at a cost), applying for immersion programs (often overseas and also at significant cost) where interaction is likely to be both extensive and sustained, and even just practicing speaking out loud while alone at home (which is productive and helpful but not interactional and absent corrective feedback). GLM systems clearly present as another potentially cost-effective solution to this problem of interaction and practice, and while the user interface is currently based on text, it is not difficult to see the underlying capabilities of the systems being extended to interfaces using voice recognition and voice generation in the future. Indeed, at the time of writing this paper, a third-party product to fulfill this function had already entered the market.

There are other potential advantages to applying these systems to the task of providing extensive conversational practice and these are with respect to the emotional component of foreign language speaking practice. Students fear making mistakes and may clam up, so to speak, when opportunities for interaction in the traditional human classroom do actually present themselves. Associated bodies of research within the literature on foreign language education including those on speaking anxiety (Horwitz, 1986, 2001; Horwitz & Young, 1991; MacIntyre, 1999) and willingness to communicate (MacIntyre, Dornyei, Clement, & Noels, 1998), among others, focus ultimately on this issue of the emotional impediments to getting the required conversational interaction for learning to take place. Practicing conversation with a machine has the potential to obviate this kind of problem precisely because it is machine rather than a human, although it should be qualified that this may only be in the interim because ultimately the purpose of foreign language learning is to converse with human speakers of the target foreign language. Of course, and in all of this, the critical issue for artificial simulation of practice, is that in the same way that motherese (or parentese) and general teacher talk is not standard conversation, teacher/student conversation in the foreign language classroom is not either; there is lot more going on besides. The question then is whether these systems can go beyond straightforward conversation and do the “lot more besides” part too.

An Excursion into Prompting for Simulated Interaction Attended by Corrective Feedback

A cursory engagement with ChatGPT, as a current and convenient exemplar of a GLM-based chat system, will convince most that there is significant potential for simulated conversations and

the interaction this provides, and brief excursion into such here allows for some low-resolution imaging of what some of the issues will look like, on both the positive and negative side, and how the teacher might productively be inserted into this. A relatively simple prompt telling ChatGPT that one is practicing for a job interview (with some minor specification of the job) will provide an interactional exchange for the purposes of practice (and again with the obvious proviso that at this stage the interaction is text-based). The exchange below (which includes minor non-native speaker mistakes purposefully inserted and marked by an asterisk) is presented for illustration.

Extract 1 (Extract from ChatGPT 3.5, September, 2023)

[Turn 1] User: I have a job interview. The job is for a school teacher (middle school) with subject specialization in mathematics. Can you be the interviewer for this and start the conversation so that I can practice?

[Turn 2] ChatGPT: Of course, I'd be happy to help you practice for your job interview as a middle school math teacher. Let's get started!

[Turn 3] Interviewer (ChatGPT): Hello and welcome! Thank you for coming in today. To begin, could you please introduce yourself and tell us a bit about your background and experience in education?

[Turn 4] Interviewee (User): My name is Kentaro Tanaka and I have just graduate* from university. I worked part-time at a cram school teach* mathematics while I studied * university.

[Turn 5] Interviewer (ChatGPT): Thank you for the introduction, Kentaro. It's great to have you here. Could you tell us about your teaching philosophy and approach to educating middle school students in mathematics? How do you make the subject engaging and accessible to them?

[Turn 6] Interviewee (User): My philosophy is that all child* can do mathematics but some believe they cannot and so do badly. I like to help child* to * confident in her abilities.

[Turn 7] Interviewer (ChatGPT): That's a wonderful philosophy, Kentaro. Building confidence in students is indeed crucial. Can you share some specific strategies or methods you've used in the past to help students gain confidence in their math abilities and succeed in the subject?

Some observations are pertinent in this exchange. First, the non-native speaker mistakes are not corrected in any way in the process of the conversation (either explicitly or implicitly). This is a critical issue for the non-native speaker wanting to use a system like this to practice. The interaction helps with proceduralization because it is interactive, but the non-native speaker of a target language will want to be corrected about mistakes in producing the target language for fear of proceduralizing incorrect patterns of speech. Were a human teacher engaged with a student in this kind of practice, the necessity for such feedback is presumed. With ChatGPT not much is presumed and the system has to be instructed to perform in desired ways; in this case, to provide error correction. Second, little specificity and context is given to ChatGPT in the initial prompt (only the middle-school level and subject specialization of the job is introduced), but the system

is quite good at initiating conversation with what it has in open questions, and given its “memory” of previous turns, context and further specificity in the conversation can accumulate as it would in human-to-human conversation. Third, the name offered to the ChatGPT interviewer by the user is “Kentaro Tanaka” (Turn 4) and the shift to the use of the first name only by ChatGPT (Turn 5) is interesting because this kind of shift is what would be termed communicative competence (Hymes, 1972) in human-to-human interaction. In other words, it simulates competence in what is communicatively appropriate rather than simply what is grammatically, lexically and morphologically correct (linguistic competence). However, and in turning over to the subsequent conversation (see Extract 2 below), this kind of competence is not always guaranteed because, and as can be seen from the extract, the ChatGPT interviewer uses the full name “Kentaro Tanaka” in a similar turn.

The exchange below (Extract 2) starts out with a similar premise but elaborates the prompt to ChatGPT with an additional sentence pointing out that the user is a non-native speaker and seeks correction of errors.

Extract 2 (Extract from ChatGPT 3.5, September, 2023)

[Turn 1] User: I have a job interview. The job is for a school teacher (middle school) with subject specialization in mathematics. Can you be the interviewer for this and start the conversation so that I can practice? Also, I am not a native speaker of English, and need you to correct my errors. Is that ok?

[Turn 2] ChatGPT: Of course, I'd be happy to help you practice for your job interview as a middle school math teacher! I'll act as the interviewer, and feel free to respond as you would in a real interview. I'll provide feedback and corrections to help you improve. Let's begin:

[Turn 3] Interviewer (ChatGPT): Good day! Thank you for joining us today. To start, could you please introduce yourself and tell us a bit about your background and teaching experience?

[Turn 4] Interviewee (User): My name is Kentaro Tanaka and I have just graduate* from university. I worked part-time at a cram school teach* mathematics while I * studied university.

[Turn 5] Interviewer (ChatGPT): Hello, Kentaro Tanaka. It's nice to meet you. Could you please tell me more about your university studies and the subjects you specialized in during your time there? Additionally, could you provide some details about your experience teaching mathematics at the cram school?

[Turn 6] Interviewee (User): Is my English ok in the last turn?

[Turn 7] Interviewer (ChatGPT): Your English is understandable, but there are a few minor errors. Here's a corrected version:

Hello, Kentaro Tanaka. It's nice to meet you. Could you please tell me more about your university studies and the subjects you specialized in during your time there? Additionally, could you provide some details about your experience teaching mathematics at the cram school?

The corrections include using “graduated” instead of “graduate,” “I worked part-time at a cram school teaching mathematics” instead of “I worked part-time at a cram school teach mathematics,” and “while I studied at the university” instead of “while I studied university.”

Your English is quite good, and these are just minor improvements to make your sentences more precise.

[Turn 8] Interviewee (User): I studied mathematics education at university, and my teach* at cram school was to helping* students prepare for school exams.

[Turn 9] Interviewer (ChatGPT): Your response is clear, but there are a couple of minor grammar issues. Here's a corrected version:

"I studied mathematics education at university, and my role at the cram school was to help students prepare for school exams."

The corrections include changing "my teach" to "my role" for clarity and adjusting "to helping" to "to help" for proper grammar. Your response is improving, keep up the good work!

Some observations are pertinent here too. First, the interview simulation is opened in Turn 3 by ChatGPT with almost identical communicative moves to the earlier extract (Extract 1, Turn 3), but with linguistic variation. Two, as mentioned above, the system uses the full name "Kentarō Tanaka" forfeiting the rather appropriate communicative move of using the first name only as was seen in the earlier extract (Extract 1, Turn 5). Third, Turn 5, in both extracts, amplifies once again, the strengths of the system in providing linguistic variation (and in the case of this extract [Extract 2] a content shift as well). Fourth, despite the request for error correction in Turn 1 by the user, the system fails to offer this correction, and as subsequent turns show, this is not because the system cannot detect such errors (it can), but rather because the precision of the first instruction in Turn 1 is insufficient in some way. Perhaps more precise instruction about where to place the corrections (at the end of the system's next turn for example) might have done it. Nonetheless, after the user breaks from the simulated conversation itself for further prompting (Turn 6) to remind the system to provide corrections, a reminder which the system appears at this stage to successfully distinguish from the actual simulated conversation/interview being conducted, errors are pointed out in Turn 7. However, in Turn 7, the system reproduces Turn 5 (its own previous turn) as a sort of clutter and preamble to the belated corrections of the user's Turn 4 confusing the situation. Fifth, when (in Turn 8) the user returns to answering the questions produced by the system for the actual simulated conversation underway in Turn 5 (having neglected this to exit the simulated conversation in Turn 6 in order to further instruct the system to correct errors), the system now does execute corrections in Turn 9 (for the user's Turn 8) but fails to also execute the next turn of the actual simulated conversation/interview. The reason for this is difficult to infer, but speculatively, perhaps the system had more difficulty distinguishing instructions from turns in the simulated conversation than appeared to be the case in the Turn 6 and 7 sequence. Nonetheless, the corrections offered in Turn 9 are appropriate and proceed beyond grammatical correction to reformulation of expression using "my role" instead of "my teaching" to correct for "my teach."

GLMs, Prompting, and Foreign Language Learning

The point of elaborating the above foray into interacting with ChatGPT is not to point out limitations with the system (or the author's learning travails), because the limitations evident in the above extracts are surmountable given more precise prompting, but rather to emphasize the point that

getting the system to perform as one wants is not a self-evident task. It involves skill. The user who is starting off, and having the above experience, would later find out through inquiry (also to ChatGPT) that instructions or prompts to the system can be more explicitly distinguished from the ongoing simulated conversation by prefixing the instruction/prompt with “[Instruction]” as a flag to the system. This helps to manage what is effectively two conversations going on at the same time, namely, the simulated conversation itself and what is effectively a metaconversation with the system to direct the course of the simulated conversation. Of course, the foreign language learner would probably want the metaconversation to be conducted in the native language rather than in the target language, and this is possible, or at least it was in Japanese, and would be more facilitative of the precision required for effective prompting. One cannot prompt, after all, in a language that one has yet to learn. But whatever the case, one still has to learn how to separate actual prompts and turns in ongoing conversation for the system, and this would be but one instance of the many micro-skills one would have to accumulate to prompt well and leverage the system to its potential.

Overall, it is clear that getting the system to do what one wants involves precise instructions, and most importantly, making explicit things which are often implicit in human-to-human interaction. When a teacher and student sit down and practice a conversation in the target language, for example, the expectations of both parties are so well set through their customary roles as to be completely implicit. Thus, much of what prompting actually involves is making explicit what we usually take to be implicit, and this is a skill which can be learned (and taught) and which one can be better or worse at, as countless users are already finding out. To some extent, this bears a passing resemblance to the requirement to think explicitly (and actually also procedurally) when writing computer code. While this requirement for explicitness may seem a burden, it is in fact a productive cognitive exercise in its own right; making the implicit explicit, after all, leads to higher levels of conscious cognitive awareness and is also related to metacognition (Dienes & Perner, 2002). It should be mentioned that the current author did successfully prompt a simulated conversation, though it is not presented here, where each of the system’s turns in a simulated conversation is followed by correction of his (the author’s) previous turn (as the user and stand-in for the foreign language learner), and with this sequence comfortably sustained in a manner which would be clearly helpful to a language learner. The variation of linguistic input is ideal for the language learner who needs extensive coverage of the variety of ways in which similar communicative functions can be linguistically performed, and amplifies the potential of the system to simulate the kind of coverage which would be obtained in natural human-to-human conversation. Furthermore, this capacity to provide wide linguistic coverage to communicative function can be amplified even further by simply regenerating ChatGPT’s responses, and the leverage this gives to the language learner cannot be overstated. All of this, and not to labor the point, is under the qualification that the interaction here is text-based and therefore not simulative of human-to-human oral communication in the most important respect. However, as stated earlier, the technology has only recently been released to the public, and it is not difficult to imagine voice-recognition interfaces with GLMs becoming commonplace further down the path. Indeed, the shelf life of an article like this is quite short given the pace of developments. Entirely speculatively at this point, such voice-recognition interfaces in the future might even give learners extensive coverage of another important aspect of language acquisition, namely, pronunciation, and do so by varying the voice generation used according to specification (US English, British English etc., if one is talking about English as a

foreign language, and even subvariants within these forms). And without running away with the idea, the system might also provide feedback on users' own pronunciation.

Situating the Teacher Within GLM-Driven Foreign Language Learning

The prospects for GLMs in assuaging the age-old problem of giving students the extensive interaction and linguistic input required for learning to occur are more than obvious. It is plausible to imagine foreign language conversation schools not disappearing (there will always be a desire for the "real thing" and communication with human speakers of a target foreign language), but at least finding themselves at the boutique end of the market as students turn to systems like this to grind out the kind of extensive practice required for fluent command of a target foreign language. Correspondingly, and this does not only apply to conversation schools but also to foreign language education right across the spectrum, the activities undertaken by the teacher will undergo some reconfiguration. At least part of this reconfiguration will come in the form of becoming an expert user or "prompt engineer" of these systems to help students exploit them in appropriate ways for learning purposes, and with the importance of this role being inversely proportional to the age of the student. Indeed, with very young learners this kind of assistance from a teacher will be indispensable as they will be almost incapable of making the implicit explicit and understanding the notion of a metaconversation with a system to guide an actual conversation. These are skills associated with more mature cognitive development.

On a more generally reflective and critical note, the above extracts provide only a very brief excursion into the probable kinds of issues which would emerge in instructing the system on precisely how to converse for the purpose of foreign language learning, and how teachers might become involved in assisting students through these issues (based on being expert users themselves). Simulation of how real human-to-human feedback occurs between teachers and students of foreign languages (and even parents and their children when learning their first language) becomes even more of a challenge when one's expectations proceed from corrective feedback as simple and explicit correction of mistakes by the system to corrective feedback which is more of the implicit variety. Taking a well-trodden example focused on the irregular verb "go," if a learner were to say, "Yesterday, I goed to soccer," the teacher might say "Oh, you went to soccer yesterday, that's nice," or "Oh, you went to soccer yesterday, did you?" The teacher's reply here contains feedback but of the implicit form with the verb "go" correctly recast as "went." Notably, the recast is presented in a turn which simultaneously is also a bona fide communicative next turn in the actual conversation which is underway. These kinds of recasts are also the typical "stuff" of parents' corrections of the speech of their young children. Essentially, such recasts are modeling correct speech at points of saliency for the learner so that they will notice the correct form. The parent, for example, does not stop the child (usually anyway) and explicitly correct him or her by saying "You used 'goed' which is not the correct past tense form of 'go,' rather you should use 'went' for the past tense." Besides the fact that the parent's instruction in this case would presume cognitive capacities which the child does not have (including grammatical terms which are part of a metalanguage), it arrests the flow of the conversation. In the case of the foreign language learner, and depending on the age of the learner, it is more likely that there will be sufficient cognitive capacity to process explicit feedback of the above kind, but the conversation would still be arrested by what is essentially a turn unrelated to the primary conversation underway. Getting ChatGPT to provide the kind of embedded

and implicit feedback which does not arrest the conversation might be a lot more challenging (it was for this author even with extended prompting, though the result may simply have been the author's limitations as "prompt engineer"). It is beyond the scope of this paper to reach into this, but it may be the case that GLMs like ChatGPT need to be trained on large corpuses of conversation involving the kind of corrective feedback offered by teachers to foreign language students in ongoing conversation and even parents to very young children. In other words, there may indeed be limitations which are related to the parameters of the corpus upon which the system is trained and which go beyond the limitations of users' prompting expertise. Whatever the case, and presuming a set of capabilities for any particular GLM is actually there, it is clear that getting the system to execute a particular capability that is available and that you require is nonetheless potentially difficult, and in any particular educational domain this points to a new role for the teacher. This role could be characterized as expert user of GLMs for learning purposes and steward in expediting the learner's path to achieving the same.

Concluding Remarks

In drawing to close, it is worth returning from the excursion into foreign language learning to teaching practice more generally and what will become of it in view of GLM technologies. It is clear that the business of exploring what these systems can do for education is only beginning. As this exploration gets underway, the central issue will be to understand how the teacher fits into all of this. The most alarmist narratives see displacement of the teacher. It is, however, far more likely that teachers will not disappear to be replaced by rooms filled with computers running GLMs but rather will find themselves having to tool-up for an added role as expert user of GLMs and learning steward for students in also becoming such. Whatever space GLMs do end up taking within the students' learning day, such space will still require interaction with and supervision from the teacher, and thus a reconfiguration of the teacher's role rather than a supplanting of it. With respect to formalization of this reconfigured role for the teacher, it is highly likely that professional teaching organizations and apparatuses will assist in the tooling up and operate as sites for teachers to share their expertise on using these systems within education. This will be in much the same way that teachers have always used such organizations to share knowledge of other developing practice-related issues and topics in areas such as teaching methods, learning management systems (LMSs), assessment, materials development and so on, and it will probably start happening from about now and at pace. Aside from the developments one can expect in professional teaching organizations focusing on the practitioner, there will also be developments in research allied to education. Very significant trajectories of research on feedback, for example, will expand from the hitherto interest in feedback in human-to-human teaching to an additional interest in the capabilities for feedback by GLMs (and how to prompt in order to get it) and the effect size of such feedback on language acquisition. It may even be the case that the micro-sociolinguistic field of conversation analysis (CA) will take a turn into human-to-machine interaction.

In the longer term, and here predictions are somewhat over-the-horizon and harder to make, and therefore come with the caution which is warranted, it is possible that the issue of how much such systems come to know about the user will be prescient. In order for such systems to genuinely simulate human tutoring, knowledge of the state of development of the user is required and this has to be modeled with information available to the system. Furthermore, and as earlier stated, here

one is moving away from the type of modeling that defines what a GLM is (modeling an extensive digital corpus) to a type of modeling focused on the learner and what they cognitively surrender. Here things become trickier given the obvious privacy concerns because the type of information being surrendered to the system is consequential. Thus far, such cognitive intimacy has generally been the privileged domain of the human teacher with professional honor codes around how such is handled, and this not to mention the rather organic and built-in right of the student to be forgotten as the teacher, for all practical purposes, forgets such knowledge in the challenge of focusing on a never-ending cohort of new students. In the interim, however, and before GLMs converge with systems which model the user's mind based on accumulated inputs, leveraging GLMs for calibrated and targeted learning purposes will involve precise prompting, and this will inevitably involve the teacher and therefore, far from displacing the teacher, will expand his or her remit.

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